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AIR POLLUTION AND ITS IMPACT ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract. Air pollution is a threat to sustainable development because it simultaneously affects various social, environmental and economic criteria related to equitable human development, such as healthy living, food security, gender equality, climate stability and poverty reduction. The purpose of our research was to determine the public's attitude to the problem of air pollution. As a result of the research, it was determined that the majority of the respondents take the problem of environmental pollution seriously, the respondents are fully and adequately aware of their own responsibility, as well as that of the people around them in the matter of environmental protection.

Keywords: Air pollution, human health, environmental measures, climate.

ჰაერის დაბინძურება და მისი გავლენა ადამიანის ჯანმრთელობაზე

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აბსტრაქტი. ჰაერის დაბინძურება საფრთხეს წარმოადგენს მდგრადი განვითარებისთვის, რადგან იგი ერთდროულად გავლენას ახდენს სხვადასხვა სოციალურ, ეკოლოგიურ და ეკონომიკურ კრიტერიუმებზე, რომლებიც დაკავშირებულია ადამიანის სამართლიან განვითარებასთან, როგორცაა ჯანმრთელი ცხოვრება, კვების უსაფრთხოება, გენდერული თანასწორობა, კლიმატის სტაბილურობა და სიღარიბის შემცირება. ჩვენი კვლევის მიზანი იყო დაგვედგინა საზოგადოების დამოკიდებულება ჰაერის დაბინძურების პრობლემისადმი. კვლევის შედეგად დადგინდა, რომ გამოკითხულთა უმრავლესობა სრული სერიოზულობით ეკიდება გარემოს დაბინძურების პრობლემას, რესპოდენტები სრულად და ადეკვატურად აცნობიერებენ, როგორც საკუთარ ისე გარშემომყოფთა პასუხისმგებლობას გარემოს დაცვის საკითხში.

საკვანძო სიტყვა: ჰაერის დაბინძურება, ადამიანის ჯანმრთელობა, გარემოსდაცვითი ღონისძიებები, კლიმატი.

Introduction. As is known, air pollution refers to the release of pollutants into the air, which are harmful to human health and the planet as a whole. According to the World Health Organization, air pollution causes seven million deaths worldwide every year. Currently, nine out of every ten people breathe air that exceeds WHO limits for pollutants. Ambient air quality is one of the main environmental challenges for our country. In Georgia, the problem of atmospheric air pollution is fixed in the largest cities of the country, as well as near large industrial facilities and industrial zones [1].

Air pollution with harmful substances is the introduction/dispersal (emission) of any substance into the air as a result of human activity, which has or can have a negative impact on human health and the natural environment [2].

Human-caused factors of air pollution include: combustion process; agricultural activities; traffic emissions; industrial activities; Electricity production; use of solvents; Non-methane volatile organic compounds [3].

Ambient air pollution occurs from both natural and anthropogenic sources. Natural factors include windblown dust (mostly desert and/or sea salt), wildfires, volcanic eruptions, wind erosion, methane gas in wetlands, space dust from comets, asteroids, and meteor impacts, and more. As for anthropogenic factors, the air convention of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe "UNECE" (convention on "long-range transboundary air pollution") distinguishes the main anthropogenic sources after atmospheric air pollution: atmospheric air pollution by harmful substances is the introduction of any substance into the atmospheric air as a result of human activities / Emissions that have or may have a negative impact on human health and the natural environment [1].

Air pollution is the fourth leading risk factor for death worldwide, after metabolic risks (overweight, high blood cholesterol, etc.), dietary disorders, and tobacco use.

Air pollution has a negative impact on the health of any person, however, children, women and people working on the street are especially vulnerable to it. Air pollution is a threat to sustainable development because it simultaneously affects various social, environmental and economic criteria related to equitable human development, such as healthy living, food security, gender equality, climate stability and poverty reduction.

According to the 2019 special report of the Public Defender of Georgia, in-depth analysis of the causes of pollution and its consequences and, accordingly, planning and implementation

of effective measures to reduce air pollution are not possible in the country. In addition, there are significant gaps in the enforcement of current environmental regulations. Thus, for the reduction and prevention of atmospheric air pollution, it is necessary, based on the analysis of available data and best practices, to take timely and effective steps both at the legislative and policy level [3].

Objectives and purpose of the research: The purpose of our research was to determine the attitude of the society towards the problem of air pollution. How informed they are about risk factors and health problems. To what extent each citizen realizes his own share of responsibility in terms of harming the environment and which prevention mechanisms are necessary to reduce the harm caused by air pollution to human health.

Materials and method: the questionnaire method was used in the research process, a sociological research questionnaire was drawn up, the survey was conducted using the principle of random sampling. 156 people were interviewed. across Tbilisi. The research was conducted in the period from May 10 to June 10, 2024.

Discussion of research results: as a result of the research, it was established that the majority of respondents take the problem of environmental pollution seriously, the respondents are fully and adequately aware of their responsibility and those around them in the issue of environmental protection. 86% of the respondents were between 18 and 30 years old, and therefore, the majority of the participants in the study, 87%, were students. A polluted environment is especially risky for children, which 90% of respondents are aware of. Participants in the study are informed about the risk factors that affect us all and that cause quite unfavorable health problems. Most people have an idea about diseases provoked by pollution. They rationally and correctly discuss preventive measures (for example, restrictions on the movement of old/broken vehicles, noise, emissions) that will contribute to reducing the level of environmental pollution and the harmful effects on human health.

Conclusion. As a result of the research, we can conclude that it is necessary to inform and encourage the population regarding environmental measures by the state. As is known, in 2021 the Parliament of Georgia adopted the Law on Environmental Responsibility. The full implementation of the mentioned law was planned from July 1, 2023, then it was postponed until September 1, 2026, and most importantly, air pollution remains a serious problem in the country.

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